

A pragmatic methodology to prioritize critical raw material recovery

Margot Coppens^{1,*}, Tom Rommens¹, Wim Van Opstal^{1,2} & Dirk Nelen¹

¹ *Unit of Sustainable Materials and Chemistry, VITO, Boeretang 200, 2400 Mol, Belgium*

² *Maastricht Sustainability Institute, School of Business and Economics, Maastricht University, Tapijn 11 Building D, P.O. Box 616, 6200 MD Maastricht, the Netherlands*

* Corresponding author: margot.coppens@vito.be

Abstract

Every three years, the European Commission publishes a list of critical raw materials (CRMs), to guide efforts in improving supply chain resilience, including intra-EU extraction and increased material recovery. However, increasing recovery rates for all 34 CRMs across the EU is unfeasible in the short term. To address this challenge, this paper proposes a pragmatic, demand-driven methodology for prioritizing CRM recovery, focusing on actionable and broadly applicable criteria. Unlike traditional approaches based on waste supply or future consumer demand, this methodology includes current industrial demand for primary CRMs that could be replaced by secondary CRMs. This creates a market pull for secondary CRMs, increasing economic viability of recovery efforts. As a first step, CRMs are assessed for recycling feasibility and industrial demand. The result is a selection of CRMs emerging as potential targets to increase recovery. In a second step, put-on-market data for product categories of interest is combined with composition data of the selected CRMs, as researched in the FutuRaM project, to identify future urban mining potential. This approach ensures that waste policies and recovery strategies are driven by industrial needs, encouraging CRM-specific recycling technologies, product-specific collection schemes, and efficient urban mining aligned with market priorities.

Keywords

critical raw materials, strategic raw materials, recycling potential, prioritization methodology, urban mining

Classification

“materials engineering” / “materials processing & manufacturing”

1. Introduction

The rapid growth of production of consumables and durable goods has led to increased resource consumption. Simultaneously, product compositions have become increasingly complex, adding to the challenges of sustainable resource management (Korf, et al., 2019; Chancerel, et al., 2013). Many mineral resources are becoming scarce and are unevenly distributed across the globe, raising concerns about long-term supply security (Wolters & Brusselaers, 2024). Over the past few decades, awareness of the associated risks has risen. In response to these concerns, methods for assessing the criticality of raw materials have been developed. Within the European Union, the assessment framework to identify critical raw materials (CRMs) is based on two primary criteria: economic importance and supply risk (European Commission, 2023b). Moreover, future trends, such as the twin transition, will cause an unprecedented rise in demand for raw materials such as lithium, copper, and nickel (International Energy Agency, 2024; Carrara, et al., 2023). Raw materials that are crucial for the strategic future of the EU, are termed strategic raw materials (SRMs) and included in the CRM list as well. In the 2023 analysis, the retrospective criticality and prospective strategic assessment yielded a list of 34 CRMs (Carrara, et al., 2023; European Commission, 2023a; European Commission, 2023b). The analysis provides valuable insights, helping to identify which materials require actions to reduce their criticality (Helbig, 2021; European Commission, 2023b).

The CRM Act aims to strengthen the EU's capacities along the entire CRM value chain, to enable sustainable CRM supply to the European Union (European Commission, 2024). The Act aspires to recycle at least 25% of the EU's annual consumption of CRMs by 2030. Closing material loops for CRMs is not a 'one-size-fits-all solution'. For successful CRM recovery, CRMs are to be functionally recycled, at least when technically feasible. However, CRMs are often used as alloying elements (Graedel, et al., 2022). Alloying elements can be recovered with the alloyed metal as well, maintaining their functionality in the secondary application (UNEP, 2013; Graedel, et al., 2022). A well-known example is the recycling of aluminum beverage cans, which contain Mn, Fe, Si, and Cu as alloying elements (Niero & Olsen, 2016).

Effective CRM recovery has the potential to improve self-sufficiency in two ways. From a waste management perspective, waste is preferably treated within the region where it has been produced (EEA Glossary, 2025). From a resource perspective, CRM recovery could meet an industrial demand at the location of recovery. As such, the supply chain is geographically altered (Zuo, et al., 2019) and the market pull improves the economic viability of CRM recovery (UNEP, 2013). Therefore, although building a comprehensive, bottom-up product composition database is crucial for gaining a better understanding of the urban mine (Prosum project, 2025; FutuRaM project, 2025), such a database alone does not provide the necessary information to determine which products should be targeted for higher collection and recycling rates. More nuanced approaches are needed to address the complexities of CRM recovery.

Several studies have explored methodologies to proceed from criticality assessments and scrap metallurgy, to risk mitigation strategies and policy recommendations (Reuter, et al., 2019; TNO, 2024; UNEP, 2013; International Energy Agency, 2024; Raabe, 2023; Tonini, et al., 2022; Gardner & Colwill, 2018). The methodologies have either a material- or product-centric approach (UNEP, 2013), and they combine a variety of parameters into a single prioritization metric. In many of the studies, the data availability (and lack thereof) is mentioned as a major challenge in the application of the methodology. The methodologies are applied within different organizational levels, geographic scopes, and timeframes, yielding different material selections. Regarding the organizational level, Gardner and Colwill (Gardner & Colwill, 2018) focused on risk mitigation strategies for manufacturers, whereas Zuo et al. (2024; 2019) and TNO (2024) took a national perspective. More specifically, regarding the geographic scope, Zuo et al. (2019; 2024) focused on recycling strategies for China, whereas TNO

(2024) put forward a list of elements that can contribute to the CRM act in the Netherlands. The aforementioned studies have mainly been developed from a (future) consumer demand and a (current) waste supply perspective. However, CRM prioritization based on industrial demand could greatly benefit resource self-sufficiency and economic viability of CRM recovery.

This working paper presents a pragmatic methodology to support the prioritization of CRMs for enhanced recovery. The aim is to select the most relevant CRMs for a region of interest, and to identify the corresponding secondary product streams of interest. The methodology's pragmatism is threefold. First, the input parameters are combined in an uncomplicated way, enabling straightforward retracing and interpretation of the results. Second, since only existing and publicly available data are used, the methodology is broadly applicable. For instance, it could be applied at the EU level, as well as at the level of individual member states or regions. Third, it yields actionable results. Due to the identification of the most relevant secondary product streams, innovative waste policies can promote product-specific collection and CRM-specific recycling technologies. In this way, we aim to provide a framework that can guide future efforts to gradually improve recycling and material recovery. The next section provides a more in-depth discussion of a range of existing methods. Section 3 presents our methodology in detail, whereas Section 4 summarizes limitations and opportunities. The final section concludes with perspectives and an outlook.

2. Background

This section compares two studies of Zuo et al. (2019; 2024) and a study by TNO (2024), which aim to select CRMs for prioritizing recovery strategies. These methodologies have in common that product compositions should be known for prioritization, but their scope of product categories and materials is different. In the study by TNO (2024), the presence of EU's CRMs is quantified in six WEEE product categories. Zuo et al. (2019; 2024) consider five similar categories in both studies, including green energy, vehicles, and batteries. They investigate so-called 'high-tech metals', which are important for emerging industries.

Another shared aspect of the studies is that both technical and economic factors are considered in the prioritization. However, how these factors are combined for prioritization is different. Interestingly in (TNO, 2024), a quantitative analysis is complemented with qualitative mapping of the industrial landscape and policies, based on site visits and interviews with recyclers. Zuo et al. (2019) employ a more quantitative approach, involving a wide array of parameters which are arithmetically averaged to obtain a set of three indices. In a later study, a more limited selection of parameters is multiplied and defined as the Recycling Potential Index (RPI) (Zuo, et al., 2024). This RPI is calculated for the current situation, as well as for a future projection in 10 years.

The three studies aim to set forth materials or products for targeted recovery strategies, and to provide policy recommendations. As a result, TNO has identified four material categories: 'high potential for recycling', 'already recycled but to be further improved', 'excluded for recovery due to low volumes', and 'excluded for other reasons' (TNO, 2024). Analogously, Zuo et al. (2024) distinguish four material categories based on the current and future RPI, corresponding to four urban mine exploitation strategies. On the other hand, the approach described in Zuo et al. (2019) prioritizes product categories based on technology, resources, and environmental indices. With regards to policy implications, this product-centric approach is interesting, for example, to enable targeting of specific post-consumer products with collection strategies and recovery technologies (UNEP, 2013; Reuter, et al., 2019).

3. Methodology

The proposed methodology aims to answer two questions in a pragmatic way:

1. Which are the most relevant CRMs for a region of interest?
2. Can these elements be recovered from secondary product streams?

The pragmatic approach to these questions is discussed in two corresponding parts of this section. In the first part (3.1), the relevance is evaluated based on four arguments: criticality (3.1.1), technical feasibility (3.1.2), industrial demand (3.1.3), and potential organizational impact (3.1.4). Data related to these arguments are compiled into a scoring system (3.1.5) that enables data-based prioritization, resulting in a selection of elements to be prioritized. The second part (3.2) investigates the product categories that contain the largest amount of these selected elements. These product streams could then be targeted in order to improve material recovery.

3.1 SELECTION OF CRMS FOR PRIORITIZATION

3.1.1 CRITICALITY

In 2023, the European Commission has published its most recent list of critical raw materials (CRMs) (European Commission, 2023b). Criticality is assessed based on the material's economic importance and supply risk. Supply risk (SR) refers to potential supply disruptions for a particular material based on import dependency, supply concentration, governance performance, trade restrictions and agreements, and the existence and criticality of substitutes. Economic importance (EI) serves as a measure for a material's importance in the end-use industries in the EU, and how well its substitutes perform in those markets. When both the SR and EI of a certain material exceed the corresponding threshold values of these indicators, they are categorized as critical. In the 2023 analysis, copper and nickel do not meet these thresholds but are considered critical because of their strategic importance (European Commission, 2023b). Strategic raw materials are essential for the twin transition, aerospace, and defense. The global demand for these materials is expected to rise, while increasing production could be difficult (European Commission, 2024). The EU identified 34 materials (or material groups) as critical in 2023, shown in Table 1 (European Commission, 2023b).

Table 1: Critical and strategic raw materials, assessed by the European Commission in 2023 (European Commission, 2023b). Strategic raw materials are in italic.

2023 List of CRMs for the EU			
Aluminium/bauxite	Coking coal	<i>Lithium</i>	Phosphorus
Antimony	Feldspar	<i>LREE</i>	Scandium
Arsenic	Fluorspar	<i>Magnesium</i>	<i>Silicon metal</i>
Baryte	<i>Gallium</i>	<i>Manganese</i>	Strontium
Beryllium	<i>Germanium</i>	<i>Natural graphite</i>	Tantalum
<i>Bismuth</i>	Hafnium	Niobium	<i>Titanium metal</i>
<i>Boron/borate</i>	Helium	<i>PGM</i>	<i>Tungsten</i>
<i>Cobalt</i>	<i>HREE</i>	Phosphate rock	Vanadium
		<i>Copper</i>	<i>Nickel</i>

The criticality assessment is used in two ways in our methodology. First, it provides an initial selection of elements to which the methodology is applied. In other words, for all elements presented in Table 1, data is collected and analyzed. Second, the supply risk and economic importance, which are quantified in the criticality assessment, are normalized and geometrically averaged into the criticality score X_{CRIT} , as shown in Equation 1. For the normalization, SR_{max} and EI_{max} refer to the highest

values for SR and EI , respectively, in the studied selection of materials (Table 1 in this case). By taking the geometric average of both factors, lower scores are not overcompensated by higher scores. As a result, a higher criticality score urges prioritization.

$$X_{CRIT} = \left(\frac{SR \cdot EI}{SR_{max} \cdot EI_{max}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (1)$$

3.1.2 TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY

Recoverability refers to the ability to extract valuable materials efficiently and effectively from waste streams using available technologies, considering both economic and thermodynamic viability. In the context of a recoverability assessment, technical feasibility is a broad, multifaceted term. But in this pragmatic approach, literature review yielded a set of factors that are combined into a technical feasibility score X_{TECH} .

Ciacci et al. (2015) have assessed the major end uses of 56 metals and metalloids. The end uses are categorized as ‘in-use dissipated’, ‘currently unrecyclable’, ‘potentially recyclable’, or ‘unspecified’. The former three are directly linked to technical feasibility of recycling, and hence included in this methodology.

- *In-use dissipated*: accounts for material flows from the anthroposphere (i.e., human systems) to the biosphere (i.e., the environment) in a manner that makes their future recovery extremely difficult, if not impossible (e.g., pharmaceutical use for zinc).
- *Currently unrecyclable*: covers material flows into use for which technological and/or economic barriers prevent elemental recycling, such as in the case of deoxidizing aluminum in steelmaking, titanium in pigments, or REE in exhausted glass polishing powders. An unequivocal distinction between technical and economic reasons hindering element recycling is not always clear, because related variables are often strongly correlated. Ultimately, a high market value is an incentive for recovery, and if the market value is high enough it is more likely that recycling will occur.
- *Potentially recyclable*: are flows for which today’s technology is compatible with their recovery, enabling them to be functionally or non-functionally recycled.
- *Unspecified*: accounts for miscellaneous applications that cannot be divided among the previous material streams because of lack of data.

Since not all elements in Table 1 were investigated by Ciacci et al. (2015), the CRM factsheets generated in the SCREEN2 project (SCREEN2 project, 2023) can be consulted to retrieve additional information on the end uses. The metal wheel provides a qualitative description of the recoverability of certain elements (Reuter, et al., 2018). Each wheel segment represents a metallurgical process, for which elements are classified according to their recoverability and the processing stream in which they predominantly end up. Hence, the metal wheel indicates the thermodynamic and process-related limitations of the metallurgical CE (Reuter, et al., 2019). The resulting fractions of end uses, as used in our methodology, are given by $f_{in-use\ dissipated}$, $f_{currently\ unrecyclable}$, and $f_{potentially\ recyclable}$.

Furthermore, the alloy use $f_{alloy\ use}$ and losses to non-functional recycling $f_{non-fn\ recycling}$, as examined by Graedel et al. (2022), are considered for the calculation of the technical feasibility score. It should be noted that the alloy use $f_{alloy\ use}$ as quantified by Graedel et al. (2022) does not take into account whether the material is the host element or an alloying element. For instance, Graedel et al. (2022) report 95% as alloy use for titanium. However, this is not entirely as an alloying element, so it should not be a detrimental factor to the technical feasibility score. Therefore, the end uses as

reported in the CRM factsheets from the SCRREEN2 project (SCRREEN2 project, 2023) can be consulted to assess the use as host element.

Note that some of the fractions of the technical feasibility score might overlap. For instance, an element could be used in an application as an alloying element (i.e., included in $f_{alloy\ use}$) and therefore be currently unrecyclable as seen from the metal wheel (i.e., included in $f_{currently\ unrecyclable}$). A sensitivity analysis can clarify the effect of this overlap on the prioritization results.

The five aforementioned parameters are combined into the technical feasibility score X_{TECH} (Equation 2). When a high parameter percentage is detrimental to technical feasibility (e.g. for $f_{currently\ unrecyclable}$), its complement is taken so that a high X_{TECH} reflects a high technical feasibility. The geometric average, as opposed to an arithmetic average, ensures that extreme parameter values are not cancelled out. For instance, when an element is almost fully dissipated in use (very high $f_{in-use\ dissipation}$), it should not be prioritized because of a low degree of alloy use. The geometric average then rightfully yields a low X_{TECH} .

$$X_{TECH} = \left((1 - f_{in-use\ dissipation}) \cdot (1 - f_{currently\ unrecyclable}) \cdot f_{potentially\ recyclable} \cdot (1 - f_{alloy\ use}) \cdot (1 - f_{non-fn\ recycling}) \right)^{\frac{1}{5}} \quad (2)$$

3.1.3 INDUSTRIAL DEMAND

When prioritizing elements for recovery, the aim should be to fulfil an industrial demand, implying secondary raw material generation instead of waste management. In other words, the recycled material can be sold on the market at a competitive price, which increases the recycling process' economic viability. Note that the industrial demand could be very different depending on the geographic scope, for instance, per EU member state. To evaluate the industrial demand, trade values are extracted from the UN Comtrade database (United Nations Statistical Division, 2025). This database provides trade values in US\$, reported per 'Combined Nomenclature' (CN) code, which is a code to classify goods trade and customs statistics. The CRM factsheets from the SCRREEN2 project link elements with CN codes (SCRREEN2 project, 2023).

Other CN codes already refer to secondary streams like 'waste and scrap' or 'slags and ashes', or to intermediate products such as 'plates' and 'tubes'. The trade values related to these CN codes are not included, as the aim of this methodology is to evaluate the industrial demand that can be replaced by secondary raw materials. Correspondingly, the trade value used for prioritization is termed the 'replaceable trade value' (RTV), including only CN codes referring to 'ores and concentrates' or to chemical compounds (e.g., aluminium hydroxide or cobalt oxides). The industrial demand score X_{IND} is calculated by normalizing the RTV by the maximum RTV and the square root is taken to apply a non-linear scaling, because of the skewed distribution of RTVs towards low values. As a result, the score in Equation 3 is a measure for the monetary industrial demand in the region of interest that could be substituted by secondary raw materials.

$$X_{IND} = \left(\frac{RTV_{BE}}{RTV_{BE,max}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (3)$$

3.1.4 POTENTIAL ORGANIZATIONAL IMPACT

The proposed pragmatic methodology should assist policymakers in developing targeted recovery strategies to minimize losses of metals in their life cycle. For many metals, the largest share of cumulative losses over time is due to waste management and recycling. Charpentier Poncelet et al. (2022) found that for 43 metals, these two life-cycle phases account for approximately 85% of the losses of ferrous metals, 80% for precious metals, 71% for non-ferrous metals, and 40% for specialty metals. Metals, undergoing multiple life cycles due to relatively efficient collection and recycling channels, are still mostly lost to waste management over time, albeit over longer periods (for example, aluminum, copper, gold, iron, and platinum).

Recycling losses may occur during the remelting of alloys as different metals tend to accumulate in dust (e.g., zinc) and slags (e.g., chromium and vanadium), or end up as contaminants in large magnitude streams (e.g., copper in steel flows). Losses to recycling processes are the largest for metals widely used in ferrous alloys (e.g., chromium, iron, manganese, molybdenum, and niobium), aluminum and zinc, half of which is used to protect steel from corrosion. The losses are greatest for ferrous metals (26% of cumulative losses) and smaller among non-ferrous (8%), precious (2%), and specialty metals (0,4%) (Charpentier Poncelet, et al., 2022).

Charpentier Poncelet et al. (2022) provide data on both losses during collection and during recycling, corresponding to two areas where policymakers could create impact:

- If losses during collection $f_{collection\ losses}$ are high, then collection should be improved, for instance, by redefining collection categories or by more selective disassembly.
- If losses during recycling $f_{recycling\ losses}$ are high, then recycling itself should be improved, for instance, by investing in the development of new or improved recycling technologies.

The organizational score (Equation 4) captures both factors. The use of complements in this score makes sure that a high percentage for one of both factors results in a high value for X_{ORG} . In other words, a high organizational score reflects a strong potential for policy impact by improving the organization of waste collection and recycling systems.

$$X_{ORG} = 1 - \left((1 - f_{collection\ losses}) \cdot (1 - f_{recycling\ losses}) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (4)$$

3.1.5 DATA-BASED PRIORITIZATION

The pragmatic model aims to assess the recovery potential of elements, and the potential of policy to intervene. The recovery potential is captured by a composite score X_{REC} , that is the geometric average of X_{CRIT} , X_{TECH} , and X_{IND} . The potential of policy to intervene is reflected by X_{ORG} . Prioritization based on a combination of X_{REC} and X_{ORG} can be represented visually by an isoquant (Figure 1). On a plot of X_{REC} against X_{ORG} , an isoquant is a line of constant product ($X_{REC} \cdot X_{ORG}$). This product is considered as a measure for prioritization. In other words, the isoquant delineates the most promising elements to target for recovery in the upper right corner of the graph.

Figure 1: Isoquant-based prioritization.

3.2 SECONDARY STREAMS FOR MATERIAL RECOVERY

The second part of the methodology evaluates which product streams to target to recover the CRMs selected in the first stage. The targeting is mass-based: only when significant quantities of CRMs are present in the studied product streams, recovery can be worthwhile (TNO, 2024). In practice, product quantity data is combined with composition data (Wagner, et al., 2021). Product weight is multiplied by the weight fraction per CRM, yielding an amount of CRM per product category. In other words, this allows to estimate the size of a CRM urban mine. A more detailed subdivision in product categories allows more specific targeting of product types for collection and technology development. In other words, the resolution of this analysis (i.e., the refinement of product categories) determines the efficacy of policy interventions.

Data availability, uncertainty, and complexity have been flagged as hurdles to building and maintaining an extensive database of CRMs in the urban mine (Zuo, et al., 2019; TNO, 2024; UNEP, 2013; Korf, et al., 2019; Chancerel, et al., 2013; Touzé, et al., 2024). Accounting for these experiences, the European FutuRaM project, funded by Horizon Europe, aims to develop a comprehensive knowledge base on the availability and recoverability of CRMs. Six waste streams are covered: batteries, WEEE, end-of-life vehicles, mining waste, construction and demolition waste, and slags and ashes. Each of these waste streams is in turn divided into subcategories. Data on stocks and flows is integrated with composition data and projected for future scenarios up to 2050. In this way, an extensive database of CRMs in the urban mine is generated (FutuRaM project, 2025).

Our methodology focuses on the prioritized CRMs and locating them in product categories. The result is a set of product categories which should be targeted by policy interventions for improved CRM recovery. The CRMs of interest have been singled out in the first part (Section 3.1), so that only data on these materials are strictly necessary to proceed with the second part. This significantly reduces the need for far-reaching database construction and management, and boils down to the following three steps:

1. Collect composition data for the prioritized CRMs, based on review of literature and existing databases. Most often, composition data is expressed as weight fractions per product category (Prosum project, 2025; Zuo, et al., 2019).
2. Collect product data on apparent consumption, for relevant product categories. “Relevant” refers to those categories for which compositional data have been found in the previous step. The European business statistics provide product quantities classified per PRODCOM code (Eurostat, 2025a). In other studies, waste statistics have been used to quantify secondary product streams (TNO, 2024), implicitly presuming continuity of current waste management policies. Instead, we rely on product put-on-market (POM) data in the most recent year for which data is available. As pragmatism is envisioned, this gives an idea of future secondary

material streams, while making abstraction of complexities and uncertainties related to future predictions, and of current waste management practices.

3. Combine composition and product data.

The main challenge here is the harmonization of composition with product data. This harmonization requires a twofold conversion, in terms of product categories and in terms of units. Products are categorized according to PRODCOM codes in the European business statistics (Eurostat, 2025a), while categorization of composition data depends on the database. For example, for EEE, the Urban Mine Platform used the six European collection categories (Prosum project, 2025), while the more detailed 54 UNU keys cover EEE by similar function, composition and end-of-life (Forti, et al., 2018). Eurostat provides correspondence tables to convert PRODCOM codes to CN codes (Eurostat, 2025b), and correspondence tables between UNU-keys, European Collection Categories and CN codes are found in literature (Wagner, et al., 2021; UNU, et al., 2014). Second, with regards to units, a weight-based approach is most convenient (Wagner, et al., 2021). However, PRODCOM codes are not always expressed in terms of weight. For instance, PRODCOM-code 26201100 represents “Laptop PCs and palm-top organisers” and has units “p/st”. Therefore, weight conversion factors should be obtained from databases and literature.

4. Limitations and opportunities for further research

This section summarizes some limitations and opportunities of our pragmatic methodology. Two major limitations are discussed here: CN code classification and data quality. Firstly, CN codes are not always as specific as needed for this methodology (Lux & Matt, 2021; European Commission, 2019). Some CN codes refer to multiple elements (e.g., 280530: “Earth-metals, rare; scandium and yttrium, whether or not intermixed or interalloyed”), hence the trade value cannot be unequivocally attributed to a single element. Other CN code descriptions refer to residual, unspecified materials (e.g., 810490: “Magnesium; articles n.e.c. in heading no. 8104”). These CN codes leave room for interpretation, and hence inconsistencies could arise when customs authorities are allocating goods. As a result, the industrial demand score depends on the definition and allocation of CN codes. Secondly, the outcome is highly dependent on the data availability and data quality. The data that has been sourced from scientific literature often dates back to more than a decade ago (e.g., (Ciacci, et al., 2015)). Not only the relevance in time, but also the relevance in location could be questionable. For instance, losses during collection $f_{collection\ losses}$ are found in (Charpentier Poncelet, et al., 2022), however, collection systems differ greatly between countries and continents. In conclusion, greater attention and diligence are necessary to ensure robust and accurate data collection. A sensitivity analysis (e.g., using Monte Carlo simulations like (Zuo, et al., 2019)) could help in assessing the effect of data uncertainty on the prioritization.

The versatility of our methodology creates opportunities towards future applications. Time-bound data, such as trade values per year and trends in product composition, allow to monitor evolutions of the prioritization results. Likewise, some of the parameters are location specific. While technical feasibility scores might be comparable for EU member states, the industrial demand score may differ drastically across member states as sectors are unequally distributed. Criticality depends on the geographic scope as well. The criticality parameters SR and EI can be calculated by downscaling and adapting the EU methodology to a regional scale. This approach was applied in the Cambium project for Belgium (Christis, et al., 2023). Implementing this approach in our methodology is then straightforward. Other criticality assessments could yield different parameters, such as Nassar & Fortier’s (2021) methodology for the U.S. Critical Minerals List. Nonetheless, normalization and geometric averaging of these parameters would again yield a criticality score X_{CRIT} that is easily

applicable in our methodology. In conclusion, the more the available data are space and time specific, the more opportunities emerge for detailed analyses in space and time.

An additional opportunity is to incorporate an environmental score in the prioritization methodology. Environmental accounting has been used in early criticality assessments (European Commission, 2014), as well as in recent prioritization studies (Zuo, et al., 2019; Zuo, et al., 2024). In criticality assessments, an environmental index was found to inaccurately represent the mining sector (European Commission, 2014). In this prioritization study, we implicitly assume that environmental sustainability is the main driving force for implementing circular economy policies. However, we acknowledge that circularity does not always equate to environmental sustainability. That said, well-designed circular economy strategies consistently aim to contribute to increased environmental sustainability, by reducing waste generation and minimizing the consumption of non-renewable resources.

The ultimate goal of this methodology is to guide policy makers in changing waste management systems (WMS) towards improved CRM recovery. Improvement is seen as CRM content in waste that is increasingly supplied as a secondary raw material to industry, in replacement of non-renewable, primary feedstock. Waste management policies can effectively improve the connection between existing WMS components or facilitate the addition of new WMS components. These WMS components include (but are not limited to) treatment infrastructure, waste logistics, public awareness, product design, collection and treatment technologies. Effective WMS policy making requires knowledge about both the concentrations of target CRMs in discarded products and of the quality specifications to be met by secondary CRMs to replace primary CRMs. The presented methodology helps to focus knowledge build-up and strategy development. Furthermore, the application of this methodology to different regions could reveal complementary supply and demand of CRM-bearing waste, stimulating interregional collaboration.

5. Conclusions and outlook

The presented methodology is a pragmatic approach to CRM prioritization for recovery strategies. It aims to advance from criticality assessments to actionable policy recommendations. Pragmatism has overall led to simplicity, broad applicability and actionable results. Decoupling CRM selection from product analysis reduces excessive data needs. Another key aspect of the methodology, besides pragmatism, is its demand perspective. Industrial CRM demand is included as an important parameter for prioritization, promoting market pull instead of waste push. This benefits self-sufficiency of the regional economy, as well as economic viability of CRM recovery. By answering the two research questions (Which CRMs are most relevant in the region of interest? Which product streams should be targeted (and which should not)?), actionable policy recommendations can be formulated. As a next step, the authors are working on an empirical application of the methodology, starting with the industrial landscape in Belgium.

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DECLARATION OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

- Margot Coppens: conceptualization, methodology, validation, formal analysis, investigation, data curation, writing – original draft preparation, writing – review and editing
- Dirk Nelen: conceptualization, methodology, validation, investigation, resources, writing – review and editing
- Tom Rommens: conceptualization, methodology, validation, investigation, writing – original draft preparation, writing – review and editing
- Wim Van Opstal: conceptualization, methodology, validation, investigation, writing – review and editing

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